

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Impact Lab

ESIL Short Course 2025

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Introduction

The Environmental Data Science Innovation & Impact Lab (ESIIL) Education Program, funded by NSF, is an annual program that builds environmental data science skills and trains the next generation of data-capable workers. The ESIIL Education Program consists of the ESIIL Stars Program and ESIIL Data Short Course, the latter is the focus of this evaluation report. The ESIIL Data Short Course teaches environmental data science (EDS) beginners from all career stages, a suite of in-demand core data and analytics skills while building EDS career awareness. The Short Course adapts the Earth Data Analytics - Foundations Professional Certificate Earth Analytics Data Science Bootcamp course at CU Boulder and is offered each year. It is available for anyone to participate but is designed for faculty who teach courses that could incorporate environmental data science.

This evaluation summarizes the findings from the second year of the ESIIL Short Course program at the University of Colorado Boulder. The evaluation assesses the impact of the ESIIL Data Short Course on participants' learning, skill attainment and development, self-confidence, and career goals. The evaluation also seeks to understand how the learning environments and teaching approaches support participant learning and engagement in EDS. Lastly, the evaluation assesses the impact of the short course on faculty and educators who receive training to build their capacity to teach data intensive courses at their home institution.

Questions Investigated

1. What are effective approaches, and critical components, which help increase participant self-confidence and sense of belonging in EDS?
2. In what ways does the instructional sequence of the short courses lead or not lead to the development of technical data science skills?
3. In what ways does participation in the short course series impact or not impact faculty instruction in the future?

Executive Summary

Evaluation Findings

Similar to last year, this year's short course participants who responded to the survey were primarily **early career** representing a range of different physical science and engineering disciplines as well as a few social science and science education disciplines. Approximately half were **affiliated with academic institutions**, primarily **research-focused**, which served both **undergraduate and graduate student** populations.

About 40% of the respondents had **teaching experience** and taught a range of classes in **science, as well as statistics, GIS and geospatial science**. A majority of the participants felt they **had the background knowledge and skill to learn EDS, knew where to seek answers to EDS questions, and are comfortable with the teaching tools and techniques**, however they also noted that **learning to teach EDS requires a lot of work..**

Respondents came into the course **using AI to varying degrees in their work**. The course impacted their use of AI in the future noting that they **plan to use it to write and debug code** and learn more about how they **can improve their workflows and productivity**. They noted that AI helped them better understand EDS concepts and how to use AI effectively in EDS. Though the **environmental impacts of AI** are still a concern for some.

Respondents came into the course interested in **skill development, research application, teaching and knowledge sharing, and broadening understanding** around EDS. The course generally met expectations related to **skill development, and teaching and curriculum development**.

Respondents came away with **increased confidence** in their technical data science skills and **increased comfort** in Python skills. Participants were **confident in their ability to where to seek information for questions about teaching** EDS, answer student questions related to EDS and collaborate with others using EDS.

Respondents were **very likely to incorporate** what they learned from the short course related to working with different data types, coding with programming languages and creating reproducible workflows. They also showed interest in **using the resources and teaching techniques** modeled by the short course instructors.

Respondents noted feeling a **greater sense of belonging** to the EDS community after completing the short course however **a majority still indicated that their perception of overlap between their self-image and the EDS community was low.**

*"Collaboration" by Eko Purnomo, "Network" by Desi Aulia, "Network" by Iakonic, "Organization" by Soremba, "Research" by Eucalypt, "Communication" by Creative Stall pk, "connected" by Travis Avery, "summit" by Kemesh Maharjan np, "AI" from Siipkan Creative all from the [Noun Project](#).

Suggestions for Program Improvement

- **Some larger datasets caused technical difficulties.** Respondents noted some difficulty working with the large datasets in Codespaces. This may be a result of participants not noting the RAM and disk space requirements.
- **Make small changes to course structure and content.** Respondents suggested adding a few more workflows to help with understanding, adding in small group activities and incorporating more analytic tools into the course (such as Xarray). Another mentioned wanting to have a Short Course Part 2. Specific feedback from one user included in the Appendix.

- **More hands-on coding.** Respondents suggested having more hands-on coding exercises in the course to increase engagement and retention. Having the lessons laid out and walking through them without coding themselves caused them not to absorb the material as well.
- **Use office hours/breakout rooms to help students who are struggling to keep up in the live sessions.** Respondents noted difficulty with managing the wide range of experience levels and getting various issues resolved during instruction time. One respondent suggested encouraging people to attend office hours and/or use breakout rooms so that some of the more experienced students could make progress during the live instruction.

Methods

The study received IRB approval from the University of Colorado, Boulder (Record # 24-0060) to examine participants' experiences and learning outcomes in the ESIL Short Course. Pre- and post-program surveys were designed to document participant experiences. Descriptive statistics and statistical tests (Wilcoxon signed-rank test or Rasch analysis when applicable for analyzing categorical data) were conducted for quantitative data; and thematic analysis was conducted for written responses to open-ended questions.

ESIL Short Course Participants

Short Course and Survey Participation

Of the 72 people registered for the Short Course, 19 completed the Short Course pre-survey (100% response rate) and 10 responded to the Short Course reflection survey (52.6% response rate). There were 16 participants who finished all the Short Course assignments for a certificate of completion. The Short Course served an international audience with 57.9% of respondents reporting that they live in the U.S. and 10.5%

reporting that they live outside of the U.S. Survey respondents were from 5 U.S. States and 2 other countries.

Education, Career Experience, and Affiliation

Over a quarter of respondents (38.5%) had earned a **Doctoral degree**, 38.5% held **master’s degrees**, and 15.4% had completed some graduate work. About 7.7% of respondents had earned a bachelor’s degree. None of the participants indicated that their highest level of education was an associate degree or that they would prefer not to answer.

Table 1	Survey Respondents’ Highest Level of Education
38.5%	Doctoral degree
38.5%	Master’s degree
15.4%	Some graduate work
7.7%	Bachelor’s degree
0%	Associate degree
0%	I prefer not to answer

Field of Study: Survey respondents were also asked to indicate the field in which they received their highest degree. These degrees encompassed a **diverse range of academic disciplines**, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of Environmental Data Science (EDS), with individuals from a wide array of fields contributing to its advancement and application (Table 2).

Table 2

Natural Sciences	Engineering and Applied Sciences	Social Sciences and Humanities	Interdisciplinary & Miscellaneous
Biology	Ecology and Remote Sensing	Sociology	Science Education
Earth Sciences	Environmental Science and Policy	Social Policy	
Biogeochemistry	Civil Engineering		
Forest Science/Wildlife	Agriculture		
Natural Resources and Biocomplexity	Geographic Information Science (GIS)		

Career Stage: A majority of respondents (53.8%) described themselves as **Early Career** (0 – 5 years of professional experience or post-doctoral fellow). About 15 percent were Mid-Career (6 – 15 years of professional experience). Another 23.1% were at a Senior stage in their career (more than 15 years of experience), and 7.7% reported “Other” (Figure 2).

Which of the following best describes your current career stage? (N = 13)

Figure 2

Affiliation: A majority of respondents work at an **Academic (higher education) institution (46.2%)**, followed by Federal Government agencies (30.8%), Private For-profit organizations (7.7%), and industry (7.7%). About eight percent of respondents chose “Other” and reported being in a fellowship.

Table 3 Survey Respondent Academic Affiliations	
44%	Research Intensive
22%	Undergraduate & Graduate student serving
11%	Primarily Undergraduate student serving
0%	Hispanic-Serving Institution
11%	Tribal College or University
0%	Minority-Serving Institution
0%	Community College/ 2-yr College
22%	Professional Program
0%	Historically Black University (HBCU)
0%	American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions (AAPISI)
0%	Other
0%	Prefer not to answer

Academic Affiliations Represented. Of those respondents working at academic institutions, the majority reported affiliation with a **Research-Intensive institution (44%)**.

Twenty-two percent of academic affiliations included institutions serving both undergraduate and graduate students, 11% served primarily undergraduate, and 22% were professional programs. No respondents reported an affiliation with a community college, a minority-serving institution, a Hispanic-serving institution, a historically black university (HBCU), an American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institution (AAPISI), or any other affiliation (Table 3).

Non-Academic Affiliations. Respondents who do not work for an academic institution described the main organization they are affiliated with, which were grouped in three different non-academic affiliations (Table 4):

Table 4

Government Agencies, Labs, and Contractors	Private Sector/ Consulting
Federal Land Management Agency	Nature Based Solutions Consulting Company
Interagency Federal Group	
Federal Government Fellowship (ORISE Fellowship)	

Disciplinary fields in EDS: The most commonly selected EDS fields selected by respondents included **Environmental Science (76.9%), Computer/Data Science (30.8%), Biological Science (30.8%), and Geoscience (23.1%)**. Fewer respondents represented Social Sciences (15.4%) and Engineering (7.7%). Sixty-two percent of respondents selected more than one response as their main field in EDS. Open-ended “Other” responses (15.4%) included: Cryosphere and Science Delivery. Respondents could select more than one disciplinary field.

Professional Society Memberships: The list of memberships comprises a **wide range of professional societies**, including those related to natural sciences, social sciences, mathematics, ecology, geophysics, biology, geography, and more. Some societies are

discipline-specific (e.g., American Geophysical Union, Ecological Society of America), while others are more broadly focused on fields like geophysics, earth sciences, and data science. Additionally, there are some societies dedicated to supporting educators (e.g., National Science Teaching Association, Association for American Physics Teachers). Several societies (e.g., Ecological Society of America) appeared multiple times in the list, indicating their prominence and potential popularity among professionals.

Teaching Experience

Years Teaching: About eight percent of respondents had 0-1 years of teaching experience, 23.1% had 2-5 years of experience, and 7.7% had more than ten years of teaching experience. About 61.5% of respondents responded that they do not teach college or university courses.

Percentages calculated over total responses

*Number of respondents = 19
Number of responses = 13*

Courses Taught: The **most common course** that those who teach had experience teaching was **Biology (60%)**, followed by Statistics (40%). Fewer respondents had experience teaching Geography (20%), Geospatial Science (20%), Physics (20%), and Chemistry (20%). Respondents who selected 'Other' (40%) reported they additionally had experience teaching social science, public health courses, introduction to

environmental science, and STEM seminars and leadership courses. The **most common topics** that those who teach had experience teaching were **Geographic Information Systems** and Spatial Modeling.

Percentages calculated over total responses

*Number of respondents = 19
Number of responses = 11*

Data-Intensive Courses: Twenty-one percent of respondents selected that they had taught a course that used data in student assignments and when teaching course topics or content. These respondents were asked to elaborate on the courses that they taught which used data. Responses include environmental science courses and biogeography.

Perspectives on Environmental Data Science: Prior to the 2025 Short Course, respondents were asked a battery of questions regarding their perspectives on EDS. **All respondents Agreed or Strongly Agreed** that they could see themselves including EDS into a class and that learning to teach EDS is good for job security. **A majority of**

respondents Agreed or Strongly Agreed that they can draw on prior knowledge teaching science to learn environmental data science (80%), they can draw on prior skills and knowledge to learn EDS (80%), they know where to seek answers to questions that they have about teaching environmental data science (60%), and that they are comfortable with the tools and techniques needed to teach using different kinds of data (60%). However, **a majority of respondents also Agreed or Strongly Agreed** that learning to teach EDS requires a lot of work (80%).

More broadly, **a majority of respondents also Agreed or Strongly Agreed** that their supervisor or department chair supports efforts to expose students to new areas of science (80%) and supports teaching new content in the classroom (60%), they are comfortable with tools needed to teach diverse data (60%), and their institution provides training and support to enable growth as an educator (60%).

AI Usage

Prior to the 2025 short course, participants were asked, ***how do you currently use Artificial Intelligence (AI) in your work?*** We summarize the most common themes in their responses below ($N = 13$).

Key Themes	Description
No AI Usage	Several participants indicated that they did not use AI at all.
Coding	Many participants expressed that they used AI to review code, write code, and debug.
Writing	Some participants indicated that they have used AI to help support their writing.
Intended Future Use	Some participants indicated that while they do not currently use AI, they plan on using it in the future.

Interests, Expectations, and Career Goals

Prior to the 2025 Short course, we asked respondents to ***please tell us what interests you in learning more about Environmental Data Science?*** We summarize the most common themes in their responses below ($N = 13$).

Key Themes	Description
Skill Development in Programming	Respondents had a strong interest in improving skills with tools like Python, GitHub, and other open-source platforms, as well as a desire to learn spatial/geospatial analysis techniques (e.g., remote sensing) and machine learning and big data analytics.
Interdisciplinary Research Applications	Respondents were motivated to apply EDS to diverse fields such as socio-environmental water issues, conservation, climate change, and environmental sustainability.
Teaching and Knowledge Sharing	Respondents had an interest in teaching EDS to students more effectively, as well as incorporate methodologies and data analysis into teaching processes.
Expand Current EDS Knowledge	Some respondents have previous history in EDS, but are looking to broaden their understanding, enhance their expertise, expand career opportunities, and explore new ways of thinking in environmental studies.

We additionally asked respondents ***What do you expect to take away from your participation in the ESIL Short Course?*** We summarize the most common themes in their responses below ($N = 13$)

Key Themes	Description
Technical Skill Development	Many respondents aimed to gain higher proficiency in Python and Github. Respondents also expressed an interest in learning tools like OpenStreetMaps and normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), as well as learn foundational knowledge in techniques for data analysis.

Teaching and Curriculum Development	Respondents expressed interest in enhancing skills to teach Environmental Data Science (EDS), develop classroom modules and curriculums, and build confidence in explaining and demonstrating data science concepts.
Open Science	Respondents were interested in learning how to make their work reproducible and open to other researchers.
Networking Opportunities	Respondents expressed a desire to learn in a structured environment with knowledgeable instructors and build a skillset that can connect international and diverse knowledge bases.

Finally, we asked respondents ***How does participation in the ESIL Short Course support your goals?*** We summarize the most common themes in their responses below ($N = 13$)

Key Themes	Description
Quantitative and Computational Skills	Many respondents aimed to grow their expertise in data analysis, Python, and other open-source tools to apply them to their research and future projects.
Improved Workflow	Respondents emphasized the benefit of learning data analysis and open-source tools to increase the reproducibility of their workflows and to increase their general productivity.
Teaching and Mentorship	Respondents expressed an interest in enhancing their ability to teach and providing mentorship in EDS to students and colleagues.
Direct Research and Professional Advancement	Some respondents noted that the course may help in providing leverage towards career goals, including expanding career opportunities in EDS, preparing for tenure, securing faculty positions, or providing knowledge needed for academic projects.
Networking Opportunities	Respondents valued the opportunity to connect with peers, educators, and researchers in the field of EDS, including international scholars and key organizations.

Short Course Evaluation Outcomes

General Evaluation of the Short Course

Participant Satisfaction and Outcomes

Satisfaction with Short Course: All respondents were Very Satisfied or Somewhat Satisfied with their experience with the Short Course registration process, communication with instructors, course instruction, course content, quality of materials, and experience learning in an online environment.

Additionally, we asked respondents to ***please elaborate on your responses to the previous question.*** Respondents overall elaborated positively on their satisfaction, although one indicated several areas to improve on textbook and notebook materials. We summarize the most common themes in their responses below ($N = 7$).

Key Theme	Description
Instructor Support & Enthusiasm	The instructors were praised for their kindness, patience, and enthusiasm in teaching and providing useful suggestions.
Clear & Well-Structured Content	The course material was presented in a clear, organized manner, making complex topics easier to understand.
Problem Solving	Some participants indicated that it was difficult getting issues resolved during instruction when there were individuals of all experience levels taking the course.
Textbook and Notebook Adjustments	While some participants thought that the textbook was comprehensive, other suggested improved readability by adding additional clarification and fixing grammatical errors, standardizing the notebooks to match the textbooks, refining instructions in notebooks, linking the textbook to the notebook to prevent redundancy, including practice code in notebooks, improving notebook naming, and including visual aids (i.e., slides, pictures, etc.).

Short Course Outcomes: **A majority of respondents Agreed or Strongly Agreed** that they can work with open EDS tools (100%), are better prepared for community building and knowledge exchange (100%), the course helped them develop a professional portfolio (89%), they were able to create new connections across disciplines and sectors (78%), they made connections with the EDS community (89%), and they can access data in the cloud using APIs (100%).

Additionally, we asked respondents to ***please elaborate on your responses to the previous question.*** Respondents overall elaborated positively on their experiences, but some indicated that they were unable to build strong connections. We summarize the most common themes in their responses below ($N = 5$).

Key Theme	Description
Practical Outcomes for Researchers	The course provided useful outcomes for researchers, helping them apply their learning to their work.
Networking & Collaboration	Participants indicated that while they valued the opportunity to make new connections, collaborate, and learn teamwork skills for future projects, the length of the course did not allow them to build strong connections.
Hands-on Learning & Portfolio Building	The course helped participants build a portfolio of their work, showcasing their skills to potential employers or collaborators.
Ongoing Learning Process	While the course and instructors were highly praised, some participants acknowledged they are still in the process of learning and improving.

Findings about Science Identity and Belonging

Did participants develop a science identity and a sense of belonging in Earth and Environmental Data Science?

The study aimed to understand any effects of the short course on participant identity and sense of belonging in science. Questions asked in the survey at the end of the short course were taken from a validated instrument used to measure science identity and belonging (Chemers et al, 2011). At the end of the short course, participants responded retrospectively and were asked to reflect on their feelings after the short course compared to before.

Prior to the ESiIL Short Course program, 25% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that **I belong to the EDS community**. This increased to 55.5% after the program (pre- to post-program $Z = 1.40$, $p = 0.162$), but this difference was not significant. Similarly, 37.5% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that **being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity**

prior to the Short course, and 66.7% agreed or strongly agreed after the program (pre- to post-program $Z = 1.07, p = 0.286$), but this difference was not significant.

*post-program survey

When asked to describe the overlap of their self-image with that of the EDS community, respondents noted increased science identity upon completion of the program, although the change was not statistically significant ($Z = 0.961, p = 0.336$).

Before the program, over half of the respondents saw very little overlap in terms of their self-image and that of the EDS community (responses A – C). After the ESIL stars program, **a majority of respondents still indicated that the overlap between self-image and that of the EDS community was low (77.7%) compared to those who saw that overlap of at least half or greater (22.2%; responses D – G).** 0% of the respondents at the end of the program saw a lot of overlap with their self-image and the EDS community (response F & G).

*post-program survey

Additionally, we asked respondents to ***please elaborate on your responses to the previous question.*** Respondents overall elaborated positively on their experiences, although some indicated that they do not consider themselves integrated with the EDS community. We summarize the most common themes in their responses below (N = 6).

Key Theme	Description
Belonging to the EDS Community	Some participants emphasize the significance of being part of the EDS community for networking, support, and professional growth. However, others indicated that the short course did not necessarily facilitate community.
Continuous Learning & Networking	Participants expressed value in continuing to learn and expand their professional network within EDS.

Findings about Skill Development

The ESIL Short Course sought to build comfort and confidence with technical and non-technical aspects of Earth and Environmental Data Science. Comfort and confidence with Earth and Environmental Data Science skills were assessed using Likert survey instruments. At the conclusion of the course, participants were asked to complete surveys that included items designed to give them the opportunity to respond retrospectively to questions about their comfort, confidence, and agreement with prompts related to different technical and non-technical components of the short course. Here they were asked to report the level of comfort or confidence they had in a certain area prior to participating in the program and then once again after their participation was complete. Results are reported using a series of horizontal bar plots, organized by trial (BEFORE/AFTER) for easy comparison. These findings are focused on technical skill development which includes comfort and confidence with data science generally, and programming with Python specifically.

Technical Skill Development

Did participants develop confidence in their technical data science skills?

The ESIL Short Course participants had some marginally significant to statistically significant gains in confidence in their coding skills after completing the program (see below). Before the program, half or more of the respondents were not confident or only slightly confident in their skills regarding using GitHub, publishing code, using Jupyter Notebooks, using GitHub Codespaces, and using Github Pages. Upon completion of the Short Course, most of the respondents noted significant or marginally significant gains in being very confident or moderately confident using Github ($Z = 2.18, p = 0.029$), using Jupyter Notebooks ($Z = 2.00, p = 0.046$), using Github pages ($Z = 2.56, p = .011$), using Github Codespaces ($Z = 2.64, p = 0.008$), and publishing code ($Z = 1.91, p = .056$). Otherwise, while most of the respondents indicated that they were very confident or moderately confident in finding and accessing data ($Z = 0.82, p = 0.414$), creating reproducible workflows ($Z = 0.82, p = 0.414$), using scientific

programming to work with data ($Z = 0.00, p = 1.00$), writing efficient and modular code ($Z = 0.25, p = 0.800$), using remote sensing data ($Z = 1.34, p = 0.180$), drawing analytic conclusions from data ($Z = 1.41, p = 0.160$), visualizing scientific data ($Z = 0.82, p = 0.414$), but the difference in confidence before and after the program was not significant.

**post-program survey*

Did participants develop comfort with their technical Python skills?

Before the program, a majority of respondents were not comfortable or only slightly comfortable with importing text files into Python, summarizing data in Python, manipulating data in Python, writing functions in Python, using loops and conditional formatting in Python to create efficient workflows, plotting data in Python with matplotlib, documenting Python code, using Python to work with time series data,

working with Tabular data in Python, and working with spatial data in Python. **By the end of the program, a majority of respondents were very comfortable or moderately comfortable** importing text files into Python ($Z = 2.00, p = 0.046$), summarizing data in Python ($Z = 2.00, p = 0.046$), manipulating data in Python ($Z = 1.99, p = 0.047$), writing functions in Python ($Z = 2.00, p = 0.046$), using loops and conditional statements to create efficient workflows ($Z = 1.73, p = 0.083$), plotting data in Python ($Z = 2.00, p = 0.046$), documenting python ($Z = -2.24, p = 0.025$), using Python to work with time series data ($Z = 2.45, p = 0.014$), working with tabular data in Python ($Z = 2.45, p = 0.014$), and working with spatial data in Python ($Z = 2.59, p = 0.009$).

*Post-program survey

Findings Related to Impact on Teaching

Did the short course build instructor capacity for teaching Earth and Environmental data science?

Confident and Comfort Teaching EDS: After the Short Course, respondents were asked a battery of questions regarding teaching EDS. **All respondents Agreed or Strongly Agreed** they know where to seek information for questions they have about teaching EDS. **A majority of respondents Agreed or Strongly Agreed** that learning how to teach EDS required a lot of work (89%), that their prior knowledge was sufficient to learn EDS (67%), that their data science communication skills have improved (89%), that they can see themselves being able to answer student questions about EDS (67%), that they can see themselves teaching a class about EDS (67%), that they are comfortable with tools and techniques used to teach EDS (67%), that they are confident in their ability to teach EDS (67%), and that they are confident that their ability to collaborate with others using EDS (67%). However, **only a little over a half of participants Strongly Agreed or Agreed** that teaching EDS required more time than they had (56%) and that their prior knowledge was sufficient to learn EDS (56%).

Intent to teach EDS

Intent to Teach: A majority of respondents saw themselves as Very Likely to teach certain technical skills including working with a variety of different data types (78%), coding using programming languages (78%), finding and using data from a variety of sources (78%), and creating reproducible science workflows (67%).

Tool use: A majority of respondents selected that they were **Very Likely** to use online open-access textbooks (67%), group activities (67%), live coding (56%), paired programming (56%), and flipped classrooms in their own classroom (67%).

We additionally asked respondents **how has the Short Course affected your career goals?** Here is a table summarizing the key themes from the responses: (N = 8).

Key Theme	Description
Foundational Knowledge	Participants expressed that the program gave them the foundational information they needed to continue learning.
Career Growth & Transformation	Some participants saw the course as a catalyst for developing their careers or for seeking new careers.
Research and Teaching	Several participants noted that they intend on incorporating the skills that they learned into their own research and teaching.

Findings Related AI Usage

Did the short course impact how participants use Artificial Intelligence?

After the Short Course, respondents were asked questions about their use of AI. **A majority of respondents Agreed or Strongly Agreed** that they used Chat GPT or other tools to make their coding process more efficient (56%), that they used AI tools like ChatGPT to help troubleshoot Python code errors (67%), used AI tools to better understand environmental data science concepts and methods (67%), that using AI tools helped them to work more independently (67%), and that they developed a clearer understanding of how to use AI tools effectively in data science (67%).

We additionally asked respondents **how did the ESIL Short Course impact, if at all, the way you will use AI in the future?** Here is a table summarizing the key themes from the responses: (N = 8).

Key Theme	Description
Intend to Use in the Future	A few participants expressed that they wished to explore more of AI in the future.
Improving Code	Several participants indicated that the program has increased their usage of AI to write and debug code.
Environmental Concerns	Some participants noted that since they were concerned with the environmental impacts of AI, they intend to use it as little as possible.
Efficient Workflows	Participants expressed that they wish to continue to learn how to use AI to improve their workflows and to code productively.

Short Course Overall Highlights

We asked respondents ***What were the best parts about your experience in the ESIL Short Course?*** Common themes in responses were the guidance provided and technical skills learned.

Here is a table summarizing the main themes from the responses ($N = 9$):

Theme	Description
Skill Development	Participants emphasized learning new skills, including cloud computing, interactive maps, and geospatial analysis.
Engaging with Others	Some responses highlighted that they enjoyed getting to know the instructors and other students.
Portfolio & Application	Some learners focused on applying their knowledge, such as creating a website for a portfolio or integrating skills into specific projects.
Teaching Quality & Guidance	Praise for instructors, teaching methods, support, and the clarity of explanations was a common theme.

We also asked respondents ***What was the most challenging part of your experience in the ESIL Short Course?*** The most common challenge was in coding. Here is a table summarizing the main themes from the responses ($N = 9$):

Theme	Description
Technical Challenges	Participants faced issues with kernel crashes and technical difficulties with large datasets.
Pacing	Praise for instructors and seamless course delivery was noted, but some participants noted that it was difficult for everyone to be on the same page due to the variety of levels of experience in the program.

Theme	Description
Time Management & Progress	Some learners mentioned challenges in keeping up with the course, managing their time, and completing all sections.
Working with Data	Many participants indicated that working with data, particularly spatial data, was the most challenging part of their experience in the program.

Finally, we asked respondents ***Before you finish, do you have suggestions or feedback on how to improve the ESIL Short Course?*** Here is a table summarizing the main themes from the responses: (N = 7).

Theme	Description
Continuing the Program	Participants suggested continuing the short course in the following year.
Content Enhancement	Recommendations included improving workflows, adding small group activities, and incorporating additional analytic tools.
Teaching Methods	More hands-on coding was suggested to improve the learning experience and increase the likelihood of content retention.

Conclusions

The findings identified by the evaluation indicate that short course participants are coming away with feelings of increased confidence and comfort in their skills and confidence in their ability to teach EDS to their students. Participants noted that they gained new abilities in areas such as cloud computing, interactive mapping, and geospatial analysis. Others highlighted the value of engaging with instructors and peers, enjoying the sense of community built during the learning experience. Several participants also appreciated being able to apply what they learned to real-world contexts and, similar to last year’s cohort, participants praised the short course instructors’ clarity, support, and effective teaching methods. The evaluation data

indicate that the course has met its goals related to improving EDS skills for use in classroom instruction.

References

Chemers, M.M., Zurbriggen, E.L., Syed, M., Goza, B.K. and Bearman, S. (2011), The Role of Efficacy and Identity in Science Career Commitment Among Underrepresented Minority Students. *Journal of Social Issues*, 67: 469-491.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4560.2011.01710.x>

Appendix

[Pre-short course survey](#)

[Post-short course survey](#)

Specific course feedback from one user:

Textbook • Improve readability and organization in Unit 1. I think the “Build your EDS portfolio” section could benefit from an overview explaining the relationship between Codespaces, Docker, and other tools. Consider including a pro/con comparison of different Python environments and clarifying why Codespaces was selected for the course. • Address textbook errors. There are scattered minor typos. Please correct the broken link to Randall Munroe in the “Get started” section. • Enhance Codespace integration within the textbook and ensure notebook consistency. I suggest standardizing the headings in the Codespace notebooks to match the textbook’s “Step 0, Step 1” format. I think this consistency would help students track their progress across different course materials, prevent confusion and streamline the workflow. Codespaces • Refine notebook instructions. In notebooks like “climate-31-overview.ipynb,” remove or consolidate instructions. Specifically, the “wrap up” sections should only refer to variables that are present and defined in that notebook. • Reduce notebook redundancy. Consider linking to

the relevant textbook sections for detailed descriptions rather than duplicating content directly in the Codespace notebooks. This will make notebooks easier to navigate. • Add DIY code blocks. To encourage self-practice and prevent students from accidentally overwriting example code, insert separate code blocks in the notebooks for students to try their own variations. • Improve notebook naming. Use more descriptive notebook names. I find the current names, such as veg-93 and veg-92, to not be intuitive and it made it difficult for me to follow along. Could also name same way as in the textbook (see above suggestion). • Clean up individual notebooks. In notebooks like veg-93, ensure logical organization (e.g., avoid duplicate “Step-0” sections) and integrate necessary imports, such as osmnx, at the top of the notebook for clarity Lecture and course delivery • When discussing technical concepts like NDVI, I suggest using visual aids such as slides or images in the textbook section. This would provide necessary context and make abstract topics easier to follow, particularly when students are multitasking